

Leveraging distributed ledger technologies for shared seamless electric mobility-as-a-service to improve sustainable public transportation in smart cities

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ABSTRACT

The use of Electric Vehicles (EV) will promote urban sustainability, decrease air pollution, and reduce noise pollution. In this landscape a new mobility concept termed shared electric mobility-as-a-service (eMaaS) has emerged over the years. Shared eMaaS comprises the seamless integration of various forms of electric transport services available via one single digital platform. Although, the current shared eMaaS solutions are based mostly on fragmented and siloed systems which has resulted to issues related to the exchange of data and services from different eMaaS providers. Therefore, there is need for integrators and enablers to achieve an inter-operable and intra-operable seamless shared eMaaS. To this end, Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) is proposed in this study to enable new business models for shared electric mobility solutions. As compared to conventional approaches DLT offers a transparent, cost-efficient, and decentralized services both for managing the supply and demand sides of shared eMaaS to improve public transportation. Accordingly, this article presents a DLT based business models grounded on the literature to decentralize shared eMaaS. Qualitative data is collected from Scopus and Web of Science database, and descriptive analysis is employed to analyze the collected data. Findings from this study presents use case scenarios of how IOTA tangle as a DLT using smart contracts and IOTA wallet/tokens are deployed to design novel business models for managing seamless travel experience for electric car sharing and leasing to improve public transportation.

1. Introduction

Due to urbanization and population increase in cities there is need for flexible, service-oriented sustainable transportation services that can address inadequate parking space, increasing operational costs, inflexibility of public transportation offerings, and lessen CO₂ emissions [1,2]. In particular, personal cars not only congest public roads but also pollute the environment amounting to almost 60.7 per cent of total CO₂ emissions from public road transportation across European cities [3]. As such the mobility landscape is experiencing large-scale innovative transformation such as sharing schemes such as electric-car, electric-bike, electric-scooter sharing, and on demand transportation like Lyft and Uber etc. [4]. One approach to resolve many of these transportation challenges is to implement multimodal and intermodal mobility options such as Mobility as a Service (MaaS) which is an innovative approach that could accelerate a shift in individuals' travel behavior from use of

private car [5]. Alyavina et al. [6] highlighted that MaaS involves an innovative application-based transport platform, which offers door-to-door multimodal mobility solutions based on a defined business model.

MaaS aims for privately owned vehicles to be partially or totally substituted by multimodal mobility services. MaaS is projected to contribute to sustainable sharing of mobility assets by minimizing the number of vehicles on the road [5,6]. Over the years the adoption of MaaS have been extended to Electric Mobility-as-a-Service (eMaaS) which is now been adopted in the society due to the increasing popularity of Electric Vehicles (EVs) [7]. The eMaaS concept is aligned with sustainable transportation as it offers a green mobility, as one of main areas of smart sustainable cities which aims to improve sustainable public transportation of goods and people through the connection of different transportation modes, facilitated with digital solutions that reduces pollution [3]. Presently, access to public transportation services

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is achieved through a single mobility platform that incorporate all the available eMaaS within and across the city while providing a single point for their use through smartphone applications [4]. This implies that a key enabler for eMaaS is that it can offer the means for complex and different eMobility ecosystems to be assimilated and integrated, while enabling different service providers and related actors (e.g., payment brokers) to manage transactions for booking, payment, invoicing, etc. as well as interact with end users, obtain and exchange mobility data, and process these data into information that can be utilized to support shared eMaaS related business operations [4].

However, this necessitates the need for a business-technology driven model that needs to be decentralized and customized to be in line with some specific requirements of shared eMaaS providers [8]. But at the same time a decentralized and open platform for shared eMaaS could facilitate a bottom-up development but is not yet existent. Accordingly, this study investigates how emerging technologies such as Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) can usefully be applied to facilitate an eMaaS offering to promote peer-to-peer sharing of electric vehicles by individuals, municipalities, and companies [9,10]. DLT as discussed in this study enables seamless shared eMaaS by providing a viable method of harmonizing of data and systems without the need of a central authority. Motivated by the capabilities of DLT, this paper aims to explore how DLT can drive shared eMaaS forward by developing a high-level DLT based model for promoting shared eMaaS which can be extended to electric car sharing and electric car leasing by consideration stakeholders involved (such as citizens, EV owners, a decentralized peer-to-peer electric car-sharing provider, electric car rental/leasing company, original equipment manufacturers (OEMs), and insurance company as well as municipalities/public authorities). This research work is aimed on fulfilling this research gap by examining the following research questions.

- **RQ1:** How can a DLT based approach drive the advancement of shared eMaaS for sustainable public transportation in smart cities?
- **RQ2:** How can a DLT based business model for shared eMaaS be designed for drivers, passengers, and eMaaS providers towards sustainable public transportation in smart cities?
- **RQ3:** How can a DLT based electric car leasing and electric car sharing be developed to improve sustainable public transportation in smart cities?

Overall, to address the above research questions, this study explores the intersection of these two developments, shared eMaaS and DLT (IOTA tangle) in public transportation. This study employs IOTA tangle as chosen DLT to develop a novel business model to help with the actualization of a decentralized electric car sharing and leasing. Findings from this study outline possible DLT based business models for a shared eMaaS platform implementation to improve sustainable public transportation via the adoption of electric vehicles as a green mode of travel. The rest of this article is organized as follows. In the next section the literature review is presented, and in [Section 3](#) the methodology employed in this article is discussed. Then, in [Section 4](#), the findings are presented. [Section 5](#) is the discussion and implications. Finally, [Section 6](#) concludes this article by presenting the significance of the study, limitations, and future works.

2. Literature review

Over the years the use of DLTs such as blockchain has been previously applied to improve public transportation and has gained research interest both academia and in industry. A review of the literature presents the use of blockchain to enhance shared mobility, particularly car-sharing and car-leasing. One of these studies was carried out by Auer et al. [3], where the authors designed a blockchain-IoT oriented shared mobility for car-sharing and leasing. The authors explored how the use of blockchain and IoT technologies can improve shared mobility by presenting a high-level architecture to promote shared mobility

combining car leasing and car sharing. Findings from the study suggested that the design of blockchain-IoT-based mobility sharing platform depends on key design principles. Another study by Wittek et al. [11] designed a crypto token scheme for charging incentivization mainly for sustainable shared Light Electric Vehicles (LEV) for example kick scooters. The study showed how a crypto token-based scheme can be employed for incentivizing LEV users when they charge and sharing LEV during times of significant solar irradiation towards contributing to a more sustainable mobility service. Bossauer et al. [9] proposed an open, blockchain-based system that supports peers to share cars within rural areas. The focus of the study is to achieve a decentralized shared mobility which connect and fosters a peer-to-peer carsharing model.

Additionally, Monrat et al. [12] investigated how to remove intermediary system within the EV charging system by proposing a solution for charging transactions via blockchain technology. Furthermore, the authors employed Hyperledger consortium platform to implement a proof of concept to evaluate the technical feasibility of their proposed approach. Also, Bothos et al. [4] adopted blockchain to design an open seamless MaaS ecosystems. The researchers discussed the role of blockchain technology for supporting MaaS and suggested that blockchain can help to build an open and transparent MaaS ecosystem. Moreover, Lamberti et al. [2] implemented an open multi-modal mobility application based on DLT to address the complex service layers and fragmented reservation system by offering a user-friendly and cross-company exchange of offers and information from various mobility providers. The application offers a distributed, cost-efficient, and transparent infrastructure for both the demand and supply sides of public transportation.

Besides, Nguyen et al. [13] designed a blockchain-based MaaS as an application based on edge computing. The authors aimed to remove intermediate layer which manages and controls the links between transport providers and passengers by employing blockchain to improve transparency and trust for all actors by removing the need to make business agreements with individual MaaS agents. In addition, Karinsalo and Halunen [14] designed a MaaS ecosystem model that enables trusted, easy, and quick transactions based on AI and blockchain-enabled smart contracts over Ethereum. The authors stated that their model stores all travel data in one ticket within the blockchain and employs an automatic price-share and reimbursements in case of delays.

This current study examines shared eMaaS to improve public transportation in smart cities with the help of DLT. Although prior studies have investigated the use of DLTs to improve car sharing and public transportation. There is a lack of research that explore the application of DLT in the context of shared eMaaS, especially using IOTA tangle, while also laying emphasis on the business and technical perspective. Overall, this study contributes by providing a novel DLT driven shared eMaaS business models. The proposed DLT based business models offers effective and efficient shared eMaaS business monitoring and provenance of transactions for electric car sharing and leasing. The business model aims to reduce fragmentation and siloes associated with legacy system and digital systems which has resulted to complexity issues as related to the exchange of data and services from different shared eMaaS providers. Thereby employing IOTA tangle as integrators and enablers to achieve an inter-operable and intra-operable transparent, technology-neutral, open, inclusive, and decentralized model across public transportation.

3. Methodology

In this study a classical or narrative literature review was performed to synthesize the existing body of research [15]. Scopus and Web of Science database was employed to search for relevant studies, as these online databases provides an extensive source for high quality peer-reviewed scholarly journal articles, conference proceeding, book chapters, and books. Also, Scopus and Web of Science database was

mentioned as a suitable database by Wee and Banister [15], and have been used by prior study [16]. Web of Science (www.webofscience.com/wos/) and Scopus (www.scopus.com) are one of the most common databases [17]. Web of Science has more older sources than Scopus, but Scopus is much more inclusive and also includes more sources in addition to sources indexed in ISI sources such as books/ book chapters [17]. In conducting the literature review the inclusion and exclusion criteria were specified to guide the selected of sources [18–20]. This study was more interested in literature investigating DLT for shared eMaaS for public transportation in smart cities, including electric car sharing and leasing business models. Hence, a structured keyword search was performed on titles, abstracts, and keywords from the selected online database.

Different sets of keywords were employed for the search as carried out in prior studies [16,19]. The keywords comprises of “electric-mobility-as-a-service” or “eMaaS” or “electric mobility” or “electric car” or “electric vehicle” and “EV*” and “sharing*”, and “leasing” “green mobility*”, and “public transportation” or “smart cities” and “seamless*” and “sustainable mobility*” and “distributed ledger technologies*” or “DLT” and “blockchain*” and “business model*” or “mobility business model” and “ decentralized business model*”. For inclusive criteria only journal articles, conference proceeding, and book chapters (e.g., not technical reports), and articles written in English was included. Sources related to MaaS and eMaaS with well-defined methodology, research question(s), objective(s), and findings were also included. Sources other than these were excluded. Fig. 1 depicts the literature review search process depicted in Preferred Reporting Items for

Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) diagram.

Fig. 1 shows the process of the systematic literature search employed. The searches resulted in 96 papers respectively as only fewer studies have focused on the application of DLT to enable shared eMaaS to foster public transportation in smart cities. Next, 12 papers were removed as duplicates resulting to 84 sources. The titles and respective abstracts were briefly read to validate the content of the articles as such 44 papers were eliminated as they did not have a clear focus on shared electric mobility or did not consider shared eMaaS issues. Thereafter, the remaining 40 articles were completely read. Furthermore, to improve the literature review snowballing approach was employed based on some reference identified from our initially selected sources. That procedure yielded an additional 23 articles on review methods as well as shared MaaS, eMaaS sharing resulting to a total of 63 articles in the study. This resulted to 63 articles employed for this study. Furthermore, qualitative data mostly related to shared eMaaS and electric car sharing in smart cities, and the research questions specified in the introduction section of this paper was extracted.

The method of data synthesis, extraction and literature analysis represents a crucial step in any review study. In this step, the selected 63 articles were analyzed, and information was extracted to help provide answer to the research questions being explored in this study as stated in the introduction section of this paper [16,19]. From each source, qualitative data was extracted, the reference was documented in word document. Through a comprehensive analysis and a careful reading of all the selected sources, the extracted and synthesized data was reported in thematic areas which comprises of EV sharing business models, MaaS

Fig. 1. PRISMA literature review search process.

approach, eMaaS approach, and DLT application for shared eMaaS. Furthermore, other thematic areas include DLT based business model for shared eMaaS, DLT based electric car leasing and electric car sharing, and sustainable public transportation in smart cities (if applicable). After the initial data extraction, final check was carried out to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the literature findings is in line with the study's research questions.

Finally, descriptive data analysis was then employed as suggested in the literature [8,19,21], to narratively present the findings as seen in the subsequent sections.

4. Findings

4.1. Background of electric car sharing models, maas, eMaaS, and DLT

4.1.1. Business models for electric car sharing and leasing

The idea of sharing has already existed for quite a while and is grounded on the collaborative consumption of resources termed as the collaborative economy or sharing economy. As depicted in Fig. 2, electric car sharing and leasing can be broadly categorized into two main business model Business to Consumer (B2C) and Peer-to-Peer (P2P) [3,22–25].

Fig. 2 depicts a diagrammatic representation of current business models for shared eMaaS (e.g., electric car sharing and leasing). The B2C business model comprises of roundtrip which is one of the earliest adopted models [3,22–25]. But, more recently, the one-way models, free-floating, and station-based models has become apparent to address public transportation needs of predominantly younger adults who appears to be less involved in owning a vehicle [3,25]. In contrary, the P2P is the most modern method in the electric car-sharing business models. P2P car-sharing business model can support privately owned electric vehicles owners to provisionally lease out available EV when not in use shared use with the community grounded on a distributed electric car-sharing fleet [3]. The P2P approach can be on a fixed rates or based on a monthly leasing scheme as the electric car owner cover associated cost related to insurance, maintenance of the vehicle. In most cases a shared eMaaS provider can operate the platform used in a P2P business model to connect the electric car host or lessee with prospective renters and collects a percentage of the fees while also providing a formal insurance for the electric car being leased [26,27].

The one-way business model is based on an approach where collected electric cars do not have to be returned back to the first pick-up spot. Thus, the car can be drop off after use either in a specified area where charging infrastructure are closely available (as free-floating method) or at other dedicated parking stations as agreed by the shared electric car provider (as “charging” station-based) [3,23,24]. The electric car fleets used in the free-floating sharing business model are centrally maintained by the electric car sharing provider (typically an

Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM)), who allows the end users to park the electric car anywhere in a defined geographic zone where charging infrastructure is available [24]. While the “charging” station-based promotes flexibility for the electric car end users, electric car-sharing providers adopting a free-floating business model are often faced with usage policy decisions made by the municipality who oversee space for parking and charging of the electric cars [16,3].

P2P car-sharing basically provides a better selection of EV types, pick up/drop-off locations, and daily/hourly prices [3,28]. Since the electric car sharing network is influenced by the location of EV hosts when compared to the B2C business model, where electric car-sharing is mostly determined on a company maintaining the EV fleet [29]. The P2P approach can completely decrease operating costs as the platform provider does not have to invest in the EV fleet [22–25]. Nevertheless, P2P business model for electric car-sharing faces some issues associated to expensive technological solutions, lack of trust, ensuring availability of EV, and insurance liability. As insurances for electric cars are not commonly valid while the EV is rented out. Hence, P2P based business for electric car-sharing has to offer secondary vehicle insurance [3].

4.1.2. MaaS concept for sustainable public transportation in smart cities

Today's cities are faced with several challenges due to urbanization and climate change [30]. The notion of transforming urban spaces into so-called smart cities emerged to resolve the fundamental social, economic, and environmental issues of the 21st century [13,31,32]. Specifically, a smart city refers to an ideal city, where the quality of services and the quality of life for citizens are improved by deploying digitalization and providing new urban infrastructures [16]. The smart city concept aims to help cities resolve these challenges by employing digitalization to different sectors within the city such as in public transportation [30]. Moreover, public transportation is also a critical component for global economy. Inefficient public transportation in cities can lead to challenges such as traffic congestion, which results in dissatisfaction for citizens and a decline in the quality of life [33]. Thus, it is crucial to also improve the efficiency and capacity of transport e.g., via the means of digitalization [13].

Over the years it became evident that improved public transportation is essential to allow flexible mobility within and across cities [30]. Prior studies also show a strong positive relationship between available public transportation and quality of life of citizens. Therefore, the improvement of mobility, transport, and logistics in urban areas is a crucial goal of achieving the capability of smart cities [30,34]. Mobility-as-a-service (MaaS) is also a significant component in urban environment as it aims to support cities in decreasing accident rates (towards vision zero), lessen urban traffic, and urban footprint [35]. MaaS aims to bring together the public transport sector operators in an interconnected, co-operative, ecosystem which includes transportation services, payment services, and transport information provided to customers [14,13].

Fig. 2. Business models for shared eMaaS.

MaaS is a user-oriented data-driven model which offers an integrated ecosystem of available public transportation options leveraging different concepts including digitalization, on-demand access, multimodality, personalized services, simplified payment, real-time route planning, with integrated services including planning, ticketing integration information, and payment [36,37]. Additionally, MaaS concept can help to improve air quality and therefore assist municipalities in attaining sustainable growth, since public transportation are key drivers of climate change [30]. MaaS has emerged with the advent of new transportation solutions such as connected, intelligent, on-demand, and autonomous vehicles aimed at providing a platform for multimodal transport through the integration of various mobility solutions [4,14]. MaaS aims to address lack of uniformity of information and fragmentation issues towards addressing the integration of different mobility services, such as bicycle sharing and car, among others, with conventional public transport [13,38].

4.1.3. Impact of shared eMaaS for enhanced public transport

In the public transport landscape, a trending mobility paradigm has surface to the forefront during the last years as eMaaS which aims to achieve a seamless integration of different forms of electric based transport services accessible via one single digital platform [4]. "eMaaS" is based on the "MaaS" which according to Kamargianni and Matyas [39] refers to an intelligent, user-centric mobility distribution transport approach in which mobility service providers offerings are aggregated by a single mobility provider and made available to end users through a sole digital platform [39]. Overall, eMaaS is an effective model for achieving public transport systems in the future [13]. Shared eMaaS is a large and currently growing market in the "sharing economy" that consist of mobility suppliers who rent electric vehicles like electric bicycles, electric cars, and more recently kick electric scooters, as well as seats in electric vehicles [9]. The shared eMaaS concept is seen as a novel approach to public transportation offering a transformative and disruptive model for the transportation domain. Shared eMaaS is changing the way citizens travel mode from just owning a car to electric car-sharing, electric hailing, and other appropriate electric mobility solutions [4].

Shared eMaaS is identified as a cost-effective alternative, efficient, and environment-friendly mode of transportation for commuting or traveling [3,11]. Shared eMaaS offers new business opportunities to traditional automotive companies [9], as such car manufacturers, such as Volkswagen, BMW, etc. are now financing in car-sharing due to their strategic shifts from the conventional corporate model to decrease CO₂ emission and become more greener [3]. Shared eMaaS has gained acceptance with its promise to fulfill individualized mobility demand more sustainably by reducing the need for passenger cars resulting to a potential reduction of CO₂ emissions and has increased amounting to than economic gains and is expected to grow to about 20 percent as the years proceeds [4]. Shared eMaaS can help cities towards decreasing the number of independently owned cars on the streets, freeing up parking space and streets to create green spaces, thereby improving citizens' quality of life [3,40]. For the end-users, eMaaS offers value added functionalities by encapsulating the complexity of the underlying multimodal public transport network using a single app that provides integrated access to intermodal and multimodal Electric Mobility (eMobility) offers, with personalized and interoperable booking of services, route planning, and payment [4].

Presently, the current eMaaS approaches depends mostly on eMaaS operators who provides centralized services to manage and control the connections between different transportation travelers and providers [4]. In public transport sphere an eMaaS operator makes agreements with private and public transport service providers to create and offer eMaaS solutions which are tailor made packages of mobility solutions that addresses end-users' personalized needs [41]. Driven by digitalization, novel shared eMaaS models such as business-to-consumer (B2C) and peer-to-peer (P2P) electric car sharing, or electric ride hailing are

evolving [42]. However, these mobility services remain extremely fragmented [43]. Therefore, as the eMaaS ecosystem develops, there is need for improved coordination of the increasing number of eMobility solutions provided to users. This complexity necessitates the need for new decentralized solutions [4]. But up to now it is not viable for different mobility systems to directly communicate or interact beyond merely reading data. This results to non-transparent workflows that impends trust for secure digital operations and identity management for seamless public transportation [44].

Having a standardized, inter-operable, and intra-operable approach is highly necessary in a secure and trusted environment that enables shared eMaaS business processes and handles business-critical and personal data is not guaranteed [45]. To achieve seamless shared eMaaS, there is need to develop a closely-knit ecosystem that can overcome technological and organizational challenges based on a fully distributed and decentralized open system, in which the eMaaS ecosystem is governed democratically by all ecosystem participants [38,43]. Such open and distributed systems represent helps to maintain data sovereignty and offers a more promising approach for eMaaS platform design creating a common infrastructure, on which different actors are free to build and run different business models. Such an open platform might provide incentivization and reduce monopolized revenue and pricing streams for eMaaS sharing to improve sustainable public transportation [40].

4.1.4. Overview of distributed ledger technologies

Emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), automated and connected vehicles, cloud/edge computing, Distributed ledger technologies (DLT) are disruptive innovations that can be employed as technology enablers to develop innovative business models to foster the development of public transportation [46]. DLT refer to a kind of database system that is characterized by synchronized, shared data management in a peer-to-peer network protocols which employs a cryptographic encrypted methods for storage of data. The ledger data comprises of a sequential links of information strung together, meaning that each participant in the network has the same data [45]. DLT are immutable ledger system deployed in a distributed way which eliminates the need for a trusted third-party [46]. DLT attempt to increase the transparency of digital system while maintaining the reinforcing security [47]. It facilitates the trustworthy procedure of append-only databases, so-known as ledgers, that are distributed among decentralize and possibly untrustworthy storage devices so-known as nodes [48]. Each node within the distributed network community has a local copy of the data stored on the ledger. Once a new data is included to the ledger all nodes automatically synchronize. DLTs typically employ consensus mechanism to reach an agreement on the stored data within the ledger [2]. DLT can create prospects for business value creation by reducing transaction costs via sophisticated encryption mechanisms, improving authentication, and disintermediation through peer-to-peer communications [37].

DLTs such as blockchain comprises of private, public, and permissioned based blockchain which determines the governance of the transactions [45,49,50]. Public based DLT allows any node user to join the distributed network, participate in the consensus and ledger creation procedure at will. Dash, Bitcoin, Litecoin, Ethereum, etc. are examples of public based DLT [8]. In comparison, private DLTs constrains the read and write permissions and participation within the network. Ripple, Hydrachain, and Multichain are some examples of permissioned based DLTs. The consortium or semi-permissioned DLTs supports both private and public DLT such as Corda and Hyperledger Fabric. In contrast to permissionless DLT, the permissioned DLT manages private ledgers with the trusted participating nodes to reinforce confidential service, higher system throughput, and lessen energy consumption [12]. Although DLTs such as blockchain are criticized for its lack of scalability [2], this limitation has now been addressed by more recent DLT-based directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) such as IOTA tangle as reported in the literature

[51].

4.2. Significance of DLT for eMaaS development towards public transportations

This section addresses RQ1: How can a DLT based approach drive the advancement of shared eMaaS for sustainable public transportation in smart cities? Findings from the literature mentioned that the application of DLT have a huge potential in many areas of smart cities. In the context of public transportation, DLT can be utilized for transactions relating to electric car sharing and electric charging, handling of interactions of EV platoon, or providing a foundation for communication between electric vehicles [30,52]. DLT can be applied in different areas of public transportation for cost savings such as managing congestion charging, virtual toll collection, and digital payment mechanisms. DLT facilitates time savings by enhancing transport network process and management operations, improved real-time pay-as-you-drive applications based on differential pricing, and improved end user experience by automating payments for bookings and parking. It can improve logistics and freight by ensuring secure storage of time stamped/logged travel data [53].

Additionally, existing shared eMaaS platforms are mostly controlled by a central operator who plays an important role in managing the connections between shared eMaaS providers and end users [2,47]. DLT has the technological potential to build a truly distributed and an open seamless shared eMaaS [43], to manage the integration of ticketing systems from different eMobility modes (electric cars, electric scooter, etc.) [54], to enable multimodal and intermodal travel. DLTs enable scalable transaction by promoting traceability, and transparency. DLTs facilitates end users and organizations to have full control of their data by eliminating the need to depend on a single integration point [37,55]. DLT can facilitate shared eMaaS by using smart contracts to automate and compute fares agreements between passenger(s) and driver promoting more affordable fares without lowering revenue to driver or electric vehicle owner [53].

DLT can be seen as a disruptive technology that can potentially change how data is stored and accessible through its trustworthy, transparent, and immutable features. This opens new business models for economic and regulatory requirements for managing the fleet of EVs employed for eMaaS sharing [48]. DLT based eMaaS has the capability to emerge as the main component for sustainable transportation providing efficiency and lowering carbon dioxide emissions. DLT are key enabler for shared eMaaS as it provides the means for addressing the

complexity associated with the entire eMaaS ecosystems, whilst allowing integration and interoperability among diverse shared eMaaS service providers and associated stakeholders such as the payment integrator who manages booking, invoicing, payment, etc. [45]. Grounded on the literature [4,42,43], other practical benefits of DLT in public transportation is shown in Fig. 3.

The immutability, decentralization, and transparency features of DLT have the potential to address some of the legal and technical challenges faced by eMaaS such as developing trust for collaboration, payment integration, and data access and sharing [37]. The enabling DLTs such as blockchain (Ethereum, Hyper ledger, etc.), are well known for cryptocurrencies, but this study advocates that DLT offers many other possibilities in the domain of public transportation, such as facilitating automated trusted machine-to-machine transactions, including bidding, auctions, and digital payments [8,45]. In addition, newer generations of DLT usually provide smart contracts which are self-executing piece of code or programs written in the DLT system and are executed by the participants within the DLT network for modelling and implementing enterprise business logic [37].

DLT has the capability to support such required effectiveness and can also boost the deployment of shared eMaaS by supporting the recording of mobility transactions and establishing an open method for identity management using smart contracts [4]. In a DLT-based shared eMaaS, end users can have more sovereignty and control over who has access to their data to provide personalized suggestions and alternatives that are better fitted to them in a decentralized manner [37]. Furthermore, DLT can promote shared eMaaS due to its ability to administer trusted authentication secure data storage and improve fault tolerance. Today EVs such as electric cars are moving data centers with onboard computing units (such as the built-in telematics), and Internet of Things (IoT) sensors that collect data about the vehicle [3]. As suggested in the literature [5,53], DLT can foster innovative options to improve seamless shared eMaaS as seen in Fig. 4.

With the deployment of DLTs an electric car could request charging energy bids from different charging stations along a predefined route using distributed network nodes based on smart contracts employed by DLT connected to these charging stations for reservation and payment. Additionally, examples of well-known DLT systems are Bitcoin which is permissionless and public used as cryptocurrency in different business sectors, Ethereum a public and permissionless suitable for the implementation of extensively usable smart contracts, Hyperledger Fabric a permissioned, private, DLT suitable for modular design, Sovrin a

Fig. 3. Practical benefits of DLT in public transportation in smart cities.

Fig. 4. Capabilities of DLT to improve seamless shared eMaaS in public transportation.

permissioned, public based DLT particularly designed for digital identities, and IOTA tangle a permissioned, public DLT that supports micropayments [45], (suitable for shared eMaaS). Lately, the IOTA tangle has been established as the next step in the evolution of DLT which is based on an underlying technology of the IOTA infrastructure (<https://www.iota.org/>) [18]. Additionally, DLT will improve trust and transparency between shared eMaaS providers by eliminating the intermediate layer using smart contracts to directly connect end users to shared eMaaS providers in a more effective manner. Therefore, a DLT-based eMaaS can provide many advantages including confirmation, validation, and formation via smart contracts.

Particularly, tickets, travel planning, and payment methods mainly can be programmed in smart contracts to be stored and validated in DLT by different shared eMaaS providers [13]. For example, DLT-based smart contracts can be employed to invoke a new kind of autonomous value share between different stakeholders in the eMaaS ecosystem thereby improving trust via immutable records [14]. Currently, there is a massive enterprise demand for enablers and integrators to facilitate public transportation. Integrators are necessary, as implementation of eMaaS ecosystems involves compatibility and interoperability between various business and technical processes within the eMaaS ecosystem [14]. This is due to the fact that mobility service providers are faced with achieving standardized guidelines for developing shared eMaaS infrastructures that integrates with legacy and vendor-specific systems. Therefore, integrating DLT systems into existing shared eMaaS systems makes it possible to interact with legacy system and integrate with external data [56]. Moreover, the security, privacy, trust, and safety in the eMaaS digital environment needs to be reinforced. The enablers may

be technical or administrative. Where the administrative viewpoint comprises of actors such as policy makers and regulators who orchestrate the eMaaS marketplace by delivering the prerequisites for the inter-operating and intra-operating data formats and open standards.

4.3. Use cases scenarios for DLT driven business models for shared eMaaS

This section addresses RQ2: *How can a DLT based business model for shared eMaaS be designed for drivers, passengers, and eMaaS providers towards sustainable public transportation in smart cities?* RQ3: *How can a DLT based electric car leasing and electric car sharing be developed to improve sustainable public transportation in smart cities?* These request questions are explored and presented as use cases scenarios as seen in the subsequent 3 sub-sections.

4.3.1. Applicability of IOTA tangle

The IOTA tangle is a distributed database based on the Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) concept. As compared to other DLTs such as blockchain it is more scalable, involves no additional computational fees and supports offline transactions which later connects to the main tangle when its back online [8]. These attributes of the IOTA tangle make it viable to become the backbone or underlying architecture for emerging machine-driven economy in managing the trading of resources such as the EV sharing, EV charging, etc. without the involvement of the intermediary [30,47]. DLT business model for shared eMaaS is driven by IOTA tangle (iota.org), which was recently introduced as the next step in the evolution of DLTs and is a fundamental technology for the IOTA cryptocurrency [57].

In comparison to other DLTs such as blockchain which is based on block creation and consensus mechanism where all participants must agree on a particular chain, IOTA tangle permits different branches of the DAG to merge. This results to theoretically infinite scalability and a much higher throughput [2,58]. It is mainly grounded on three main advantages; as being scalable, involving no fees unlike in Ethereum or Bitcoin, and allows for offline transactions. These features of the tangle and its cryptocurrency make it a more suitable backbone for emerging machine-driven economy which enables machines such as electric cars, charging stations, and tolls to trade resources and services with each other and make feasible, micropayments between themselves without additional transaction fees [57]. IOTA tangle transfer assets e.g., via MIOTA or through simple messages using zero-value transactions which issue transactions to an individual receiver address and all transactions are stored in the tangle [2,58].

One of the predominant challenges in public based DLT designs such as IOTA is data confidentiality. As such IOTA tangle integrates a messaging channel called Masked Authenticated Messaging (MAM) approach to resolve this setback [2]. Accordingly, IOTA tangle increases the transparency of the public transportation system while reinforcing a high level of privacy and data sovereignty via digital identity management. The tangle support Machine-to-Machine (M2M) transactions,

increased security, and the automation of shared eMaaS processes without the involvement of the intermediary. IOTA tangle supports micropayments where a small amounts of MIOTA is effectively transferred among two IOTA addresses via flash channels which are primarily based on off-chain communication amongst contracting parties based on a multi-signature address within the tangle [2].

4.3.2. Use case scenario for IOTA tangle based electric car leasing

IOTA tangle is employed in this study to design a novel business model as a permissionless shared eMaaS marketplace for public transportation and does not rely on central intermediaries. The business model employs IOTA tangle as an integrator and enabler to achieve an inter-operable and intra-operable seamless shared eMaaS infrastructure. The model transcends beyond organizational borders and across the transportation sectors providing an open peer-to-peer decentralized shared eMaaS solution to electric mobility service providers using the MIOTA cryptocurrency which converts payment to the deserved currency of end users. The business model concept for electric car leasing is shown in Fig. 5, where electric mobility service providers publish their available or registered electric mobility assets such as offers and electric cars vehicle information publicly within the IOTA tangle network. This information is searched and queried by potential end users. Once an end

Fig. 5. DLT driven business model for electric car leasing.

users found a suitable eMaaS offer based on the available EV location, the agreement of the travel details for the journey such as the destination and price based on the pay-per-use micropayments is changed during the journey managed by smart contracts which connects with the end users and the electric vehicle via tokenization.

Fig. 5 illustrates the DLT based business model to support shared eMaaS towards the actualization of potential benefits or KPIs in smart cities. As suggested in the literature [2], the registration procedure for a particular EV basically requires sending a check-in communication for an EV location based on the IOTA address by the electric mobility service provider. In the case of an electric car during the initial registration the identity of the user will be verified if the user has an active driver's license, this is checked and automatically approved within the tangle by the electric mobility service provider or via an API which gets access to the department of public transportation. However, foreigner drivers from other countries must upload a copy of his/her driver license which is verified during registration by the electric mobility service provider connected by tangle and then confirmation is sent by e-mail. Thus, he/she must also provide e-mail address, telephone number, address and payment option which is linked to the IOTA wallet provided by tangle. An end user as a driver can select one of the available EV (e.g., an electric car), by using a shared eMaaS app which directly connects via Bluetooth (to get in touch with the electric car for keyless), to the electric car and sends the initially planned destination. Then the smart contracts deployed in the electric car calculates the travel fare to the initially specified destination which is to be agreed upon by the driver. Similarly, Fig. 6 depicts the flow of the business process for a user when renting and using an electric car.

Following, IOTA tangle opens a micropayment channel which is linked to the IOTA wallet of the driver and the electric car. After the driver approves and transfers the initial microtransaction, the electric car door unlocks. The driver proceeds to remove the charging cables connected to the charging station pole if the electric car is plugged and charging and puts the charging cable of the EV inside the boot of the electric car and the user can start his/her trip. During the journey, payments will be charged to the driver over the tangle-based micropayment channel to the electric car based on each meter traveled or elapsed time in seconds. Once the driver arrives at the specified destination the driver selects "return electric car" and the micropayment

channel is ended, and the electric car is parked and connects the electric car to an available charging station and check that charging has started so that it has sufficient energy and can be used by another user.

Overall, the smart contract powered by IOTA tangle comprises of EV information (ID, vehicle channel, and channel ID), vehicle information (vehicle channel information which comprises of metadata for a particular EV, stop, welcome, and disembarking messages based on the physical location of the EV [4,12]. It also includes trip information such as the check-in messages for the EV, price information, payment address, trip channel accessible for reservation or on a trip, departed message, and stop address. The last information comprises of micropayment channel, payment granularity, pay-per-use mode for EVs [4]. The tangle employs tokens which are mostly utilized in real time as unique identifiers for trust and security of transactions including booking payment [14], and ticketing reflected in the IOTA wallet in IOTA token (MIOTA) and stored in the tangle network. The use of tokens by tangle offers the possible of less transaction fees via micro payments [4].

Using smart contracts travel tickets can be specified and be utilized in ways such that users can access several eMaaS operators [59]. The service fee linked to the ticket sale can be held in by escrow till the user selects a particular eMaaS operator to increased transparency. Data stored on the tangle may also include data from users' trips and access rights. By providing governance access and ownership rights to the decentralized storage, the tangle can be more effective and the immutability of DLT can be maintained. The data can also be encrypted to provide selective access rights and will be made accessible to the user who provided the data or is given permission access. This will improve the security and privacy of personal data which is encrypted and accessible only by parties that have legal right to access the information or are participants of the transactions. Tangle also improves transparency of transactions via tokenized data stored in the tangle resulting to added trust to the shared eMaaS business model for travelers as data are not centrally controlled by any entity and cannot be altered or deleted offering additional flexibility [4], as mentioned in the literature [45].

4.3.3. Use case scenario for IOTA tangle based electric car sharing

Shared eMaaS is now being adopted as a means of public transportation for citizens to get around instead of traveling alone. This has

Fig. 6. Flow diagram for the DLT driven business model for electric car leasing.

potential for reducing environmental burdens, thereby saving costs and resources. Although other means of public transportation such as electric buses, railways, and subways (underground trains) are characterized by fixed schedules and routes, shared use of electric vehicles offers greater flexibility. In addition, the benefits also include faster travel, convenience, and comfort. This pertains particularly to rural areas, where it is much difficult to organize frequent public transportation services. Electric car sharing is referred to in this setting as the shared use of an electric vehicle by two or more people with similar travel needs, who usually divide up the incurred transport costs. In the context of electric car sharing, there is a driver offering transportation service and one or more persons as passengers who ride with him/her [45]. Practically, there are three distinct electric car sharing business models which have emerged as seen in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 present business models that can be employed to facilitate electric car sharing to boost sustainable public transportation. However, in practice most eMaaS operators adopts two or all three of these business models specified in Fig. 7. In the “one-off ride offers” and “regular commute” business models the smart contract linked to IOTA tangle creates a bilateral agreement between the driver and passenger(s). Important information, such as the time and meeting location are specified in the eMaaS app for all parties involved. Whereas in the case of the “ad hoc” business model potential passengers usually use the eMaaS app to post a request for a ride based on a certain route and a matching algorithm integrated with IOTA tangle via Application Programming Interface (API) then searches for offers from geographically available drivers that match such search. Practically these ride requests are later displayed to drivers within the same geographical area in the eMaaS app. Once a driver accepts any of the offers or request from passenger(s) the smart contract as an “escrow” deploys an agreement between all parties and the driver agrees to picks the passenger(s) at a designated location indicated by the app.

Smart contract creates a standardized digital agreement which comprise of metadata on the ride (e.g., date, time, route, start time, pickup locations, end time driver, and number of passengers, price split). Smart contract supports the participating parties (driver and passenger (s)) to approve the ride transaction using their private keys to access the tangle which saves the trip history into the tangle [26]. But in situation of disputes where one or two participants refuses to approve a mediator who has been previously selected and specified in the smart contract can be summoned. The eMaaS app will have a payment interface that lets all partners to pay for the splitted fees in cryptocurrencies such as IOTA token (MIOTA) or local currency via the IOTA wallet using their handheld device [45]. Moreover, incentives as tokens can be disbursed to drivers and passengers’ willingness to participate in the electric car sharing. The incentives can be used to pay for or compensate drivers and

passengers for their active involvement. The tokens are valued in comparison with exchange rate of the local currency (as managed by smart contracts) and could be used for as a substitute means of payment when sharing electric cars. Tangle can automate this process without the involvement of a third party which disbursed the drivers and passengers as in the conventional mobility platform [45].

IOTA tangle can be deployed as backbone to support each of the three business models represented in Fig. 7 due to its decentralized database for data and transactions storage. Moreover, M2M communication with subscription behavior Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) connectivity protocol can be employed for inter-device communication with the driver/passenger handheld devices with the electric vehicle. MQTT is suggested as it employs a M2M IoT connectivity protocol. It is a particularly lightweight and employs a publish-subscribe messaging transport protocol. These attributes make it valuable in real life situations, which involves a constant communication environment such as in electric car sharing where the electric car needs to communicate with the handheld devices of the passengers and driver. MQTT ensures instant transfer of data and transactions value with high throughput [57]. Using the publish and subscribe technique it can publish and receive messages from server to client making easy communication between electric car and handheld devices such as mobile phones. Furthermore, to allow secure value transactions for electric car sharing.

Lately, a bi-directional payment channel called the Flash Channel (FC), has been established which adapts to the MQTT protocol. It allows both service providers and resource to get rewarded for their services while in execution. Thus, FCs aids real-time streaming of transactions, and allow infrastructure to transmit data and value through protocol such as MQTT and then integrates the results with the main IOTA tangle in an inter-operable manner. Avoiding waiting time required for transactions to be authorized within the IOTA network [57]. Therefore, adopting tangle for electric car sharing prevents the formation of monopoly (supports inclusive mobility, avoid arbitrary price setting, and address data silos), foster trust and identity among the passengers and driver (lessen individuals revealing unnecessary data), and lastly facilitates payment settlement without the involvement of third parties [45].

5. Discussion and implications

5.1. Discussion

The sharing economy concept can be very beneficial for cities, as this can lessen the total amount of waste. Shared eMaaS refers to the shared use of an EV by different people with similar mobility requirements promoting a shift in paradigm regarding green mobility. The adoption of

Fig. 7. Possible business models for electric car sharing.

eMaaS is constantly growing, and perhaps will continue to expand in the upcoming years [55]. eMaaS aims to provide an integrated access to various electric transport services towards creating an economical alternative to privately owned cars towards the decrease of privately owned vehicles in municipalities. Additionally, in the context of public transportation, eMaaS solutions such as electric car sharing, and leasing can help with reducing traffic jams or road congestion, improve EV utilization, and decreasing emissions. Nevertheless, there are some concerns relating to electric car sharing and leasing, such as silos systems and data complexity resulting to data inter-operability, intra-operability, privacy, and security issues. Other related issues relate to the risk of monopolies arising, transparent billing system to prevent fraud, identity management and trust among the parties involved. For instance, there is a need to create trust among driver and passengers(s) [45]. Additionally, most of the existing electric mobility sharing solutions are managed and regulated by a centralized intermediary, resulting in one single point of failure (Cassano, 2015; [30]).

Using DLT such as blockchain in the context of car sharing and leasing has been reported in the literature (see Section 2). Findings from Koh et al. [60]; Vega Medel [55]; Karlson'Charlie'Hargroves and Stantic [53] stated that use of DLTs such as blockchain in the sharing economy has the potential to lower ride costs for the driver or vehicle. It also creates the possibility for transparent, technology-neutral, open, inclusive, and decentralized ride sharing businesses models that reduces monopoly in public transportation. Our findings suggest DLT as one possible technology that can advance shared eMaaS by facilitating inter-organizational collaboration between several actors within car-sharing and leasing and eliminates the need of intermediaries. The use of DLT for supporting shared eMaaS is a promising alternative to centralized approach as it employs smart contracts that reduces transactions cost removing difficulties associated with payment systems [4], without any intermediary by automatically disbursing the agreed amount after all participants have approved with their private keys [45]. DLT can help for storing metadata of drivers and passengers and automate this process without the need to involve intermediaries. DLT can also be employed to develop an incentive system that rewards active participants involved in shared eMaaS by giving them tokens that could also be used to pay for electric mobility services via the eMaaS platform [45].

Technically, due to its decentralized nature and its capability to automate business processes over smart contracts, DLT is well-suitable for executing bilateral business transactions and for reducing the risk of monopolies [61]. Although, the potential of DLT such as blockchain is limited by technological constraints such as high energy consumption and latency. IOTA tangle is suggested in this study as it is scale and consumes less energy as compared to blockchain. Additionally, there are complexities associated with matching ride offers provided by drivers with potential passengers, due to the large datasets that must be continuously processed, analyzed, and updated. IOTA tangle could be used to manage electric car sharing supply and demand towards providing an open and multimodal public transportation in terms of trust creation and digital identity management. Overall, the IOTA tangle can help to foster trust between shared electric car provider, offer flexibility for new shared electric car provider to freely participate within the eMaaS ecosystem, and improves transparency between shared electric car provider, drivers, and passengers within the decentralized network. IOTA tangle can be used for privacy preserving authentication and identification of drivers and passengers. IOTA tangle aids for identity management after ride demand and supply have been matched using the digital identity a driver can prove to his passenger(s) that he/she has a legitimate driver's license. As the driver's license would have previously been digitally verified within the distributed ledger.

Motivated by the growing interest in shared electric mobility in smart cities, this research study examines how DLT especially IOTA tangle can drive the advancement of shared eMaaS, specifically for electric car-sharing and leasing to improve public transportation. This

research proposed business models to promote shared eMaaS in public transportation. Another example of new business model and service that IOTA tangle can support is automated payment for certain mobility services such as parking and recharging of electric vehicles [62]. Findings from Anthony Jnr et al., [7]; Auer et al. [3] suggested that shared eMaaS can facilitate personalized mobility demands in a greener way by creating a source of revenue, reducing CO₂ emissions, and opening up space for the community. Overall, electric car leasing allows individuals to use locally available electric cars at any time and duration for a certain fee. It differs from ride-hailing services, taxis, or carpooling as the renters themselves can drive the electric car and the shared electric car provider is more flexible as regards to the duration of use and pick-up/drop-off location [3]. In addition, evidence from Fridgen et al. [45] suggested that DLT can foster identity management and design of trust-based system identification and authentication of participants in a manner where their privacy is respected. This enables the registration and authorization of drivers and passengers without the need for them to have multiple user account. It would also make it easy for them to switch to another provider. For another, DLT could be used to resolve a previously identified trust issue between drivers and passengers.

5.2. Research implications

In order to overcome technological and business driven challenges associated with managing shared eMaaS for EV sharing and leasing such as scalability, non-standardization, and intra-operability, inter-operability, of silos systems. This study contributes as only fewer studies have investigated the decentralized business models based on corporate and technical perspective in relation to electric car-sharing and leasing. Furthermore, this article design novel business models to decentralize shared eMaaS by adopting DLT based IOTA tangle as enabler to address the aforementioned challenges faced by shared eMaaS towards improve public transportation. The developed business models aimed to create an ecosystem that manage complexity issues associated with electric car leasing and sharing. Theoretically this study provides more in-depth analysis grounded on the literature on how DLTs such as IOTA tangle may advance the development of electric car-sharing and leasing in smart cities by presenting applicable business models that can be employed to achieve an integrated shared eMaaS as shown in Fig. 5–7.

Overall, the develop business model provides a decentralized, open peer-to-peer approach based on IOTA tangle to enable a reliable and immutable management of shared eMaaS, while automating electric car sharing and leasing between involved parties. The deployment of IOTA tangle in the developed business model allows for fast, accurate, and free payments utilizing MIOTA (which is the general denominator of IOTA's cryptocurrency) [2]. Evidence from this study advocate that the use of IOTA tangle can advance electric car-sharing and electric car-leasing by enabling inter-enterprise collaboration and minimizing the need for trust between different stakeholders. As pointed out by Lopez and Farooq [63] DLT like IOTA tangle have the potential to give the individuals full control of their data, protect individual's private travel information and secure their privacy. As it is difficult to tamper with IOTA tangle and data transactions are secure and transparent to all participants, including the entities who produced the data. As such, IOTA tangle offers a solution for developing a decentralized network for mobility data and related services, where drivers and passengers can own and access their mobility data, as all transactions are secure, fair, and democratic.

With the high need for public transportation, shared eMaaS is regarded as one of the best solutions for sustainable transportation strategy. However, the current shared eMaaS are based on a centralized business model which has resulted in complexities, lack flexibility, trust, and transparency which has resulted to difficulty in actualizing an inter-operable and intra-operable business model [3]. This research emphasizes on how DLT can facilitate a seamless peer-to-peer electric car-sharing and leasing experience initiated by IOTA tangle to avoid data silos of digital and legacy systems that do not communicate with each other

which has resulted to high expenses in the form of data integration, possible mishandling and fraud, waste of resources, missing information resulting in errors, and lost time [3]. Findings from this article provides an open and inclusive governance approach for shared eMaaS, where everyone (drivers and passengers), can connect to any electric vehicle service providers via a trusted connection in a peer-to-peer manner for sharing of data, public transport plans, and timetables.

5.3. Practical implications

Nowadays, public transportation infrastructures are presently experiencing an unparalleled revolution. Major advances in digitalization are the driving force behind this transformation [42]. DLTs has actively been adopted due to digitalization in the transportation domain to manage business and non-business operations [63]. However, prior studies did not provide evidence based on the technical requirements of a decentralized EV sharing and leasing eco-system linked to industrial-specific business implications [3]. In addition, existing studies on the use of DLT in MaaS predominantly employ blockchain as DLT. The throughput of blockchains based platforms are restricted which has results to poor scalability. Therefore, this study suggests an alternative DLT such as IOTA tangle which is based on the DAG as it is have the potential to provide a much scalable business model for shared eMaaS. Moreover, IOTA tangle is more cost-efficient as compared to blockchain based solutions which requiring transaction fees. IOTA tangle is open for a broad range of participants such as the eMaaS providers, passengers, and drivers, municipalities, etc. Accordingly, this study advocates for the adoption of IOTA tangle as a DLT to improve shared eMaaS.

The adoption of IOTA tangle facilitates a shared electric car sharing and leasing by enabling a unified and inter-operable and intra-operable matching, reservation, and payment of electric mobility offerings. Findings from this study presents a new business model to digitalize the existing shared electric mobility sector employing IOTA tangle as an integrators and enablers to address fragmented and siloed systems which has resulted to complexity issues faced by shared eMaaS providers. This study employ a decentralized peer-to-peer electric mobility concept for electric car supply (electric car sharing/leasing company) and demand sides (passengers and drivers) to develop an open shared eMaaS marketplace to improve public transportation. The business model eliminates any middleman as MQTT, and smart contract are deployed to orchestrate and creates a more transparent pricing to all participants within the shared eMaaS ecosystem. IOTA wallets and tokens are used to streamlining electric car sharing and leasing process based on inter-operable and intra-operable sharing of data and resources managed by IOTA tangle resulting to decrease of data silos in the shared platforms and reduce complexity for better performance and efficiency.

6. Conclusion

Overall, the sharing economy aims to take value of underutilized resources or assets, such as electric vehicles, and make them accessible via a digital means to a larger community, leading to a decreased need for ownership. Due to this notion, many transport incumbents and mobility start-ups have high interest in shared electric mobility services [54]. Accordingly, research and development on new electric mobility related services is focused on the sharing business model. Shared eMaaS is part of the sharing economy model, which aims for a sustainable (profitable, social, and environmental), society. Although, the current shared eMaaS solutions are mostly based on fragmented and siloed as they are driven be centralized business models which has resulted to complexity issues as related to the exchange of information and services from different eMaaS providers. Therefore, there is need for integrators and enablers to achieve an inter-operable and intra-operable electric mobility services. In addition, in line with digitalization in the public transportation, there is need to address silos and aggregation of inter-modal and multimodal services leading to the development of

sustainable mobility in smart cities.

It is necessary to aggregate all shared eMaaS driven by DLTs such as IOTA tangle to innovate business models that transits from a vehicle-centric to a user-centric approach [3]. Therefore, this article presents a DLT based business model grounded on the literature to decentralize shared eMaaS. The designed business model aids to digitalize the existing shared electric mobility sector. As compared to conventional approaches by employing IOTA tangle it offers a transparent, cost-efficient, and distributed services both for managing the supply and demand sides of eMaaS to improve public transportation. Although this study is most grounded on qualitative data collected from Scopus and Web of Science database. There is need for primary data to further validate the business model based on real life use case scenarios. In future studies this study will continue in the research path of investigating the convergence of AI and DLT to creates new business model of datafication among participating partners and stakeholders towards achieving complete openness, transparency, inclusiveness, equality, and autonomous shared eMaaS. In addition, data will be collected from relevant actors to validate the developed business models as related to its usability and effectiveness in improving electric car sharing and leasing.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bokolo Anthony Jnr: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

There is no conflicts of interest.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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